

Saurashtra University, Rajkot, for facilities. One of the authors (R.N.V.) thanks Gujarat State Government for awarding research scholarship and the other (K.P.R.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi for awarding Junior Research Fellowship. Authors also thank to R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Bombay for the spectral analysis.

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Synthesis of 2,4-Disubstituted-1,5-quinoxalinodiazepines

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Manuscript received 18 May 1987, revised 26 September 1988, accepted 4 October 1988

DIAZEPINE derivatives possess wide therapeutic activity^{1,2}. With a view to get better therapeutic agents, we have prepared several new 2,4-disubstituted-1,5-quinoxalinodiazepines (3) by condensing 2,3-diaminoquinoxaline (1) and different 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds (2) in boiling ethanolic medium in presence of a little glacial acetic acid (Scheme 1). Compound 1 was prepared from oxamide and *o*-phenylenediamine. The structure of 3 was established on the basis of chemical analysis and ir spectral data.

Experimental

The required β -diketones (2) were prepared following the known procedure^{3,4}.

2,3-Diaminoquinoxaline (1): A mixture of the oxamide (12 g), *o*-phenylenediamine (14.8 g), dry dioxane (70 ml) and a few ml of dilute HCl was refluxed for 18 h. The solvent was then removed to get a solid which was dissolved in warm water (250 ml). The solution was cooled in an ice-bath to yield

Scheme 1

shiny yellow crystals (6 g) recrystallised from water, m.p. 331°d.

2,4-Disubstituted-1,5-quinoxalinodiazepines (3): Details of the typical experiment (where R=R'=phenyl) are as follows. A mixture of 2,3-diaminoquinoxaline (8 g), dibenzoylmethane (11.2 g), ethanol (75 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitate formed was crystallised from ethanol, (56%), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 78.01; H, 4.30; N, 15.05. C₂₂H₁₆N₄ requires: C, 79.01; H, 4.50; N, 15.45%); its alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with HCl indicating the diazepine structure; ν_{max} 1590 (C=N) and 1340 cm⁻¹ (C-N); δ 3.2 (2H, s, CH₂) and 6.9-8.32 (14H, m, ArH) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.p °C	Yield %
3a	H	H	H	H	H	125	56
3b	H	H	Cl	H	H	155	40
3c	H	H	Br	H	H	131	38
3d	H	H	OH ₂	H	H	98	39
3e	H	H	OOH ₂	H	H	149	39
3f	OH	H	H	H	H	138	40
3g	OH	Cl	H	H	H	220	45
3h	OH	H	H	Cl	H	221	45
3i	OH	OH ₂	H	H	H	150	48
3j	OH	OOH ₂	H	H	H	209	45
3k	OH	Cl	H	Cl	H	180	40
3l	OH	Br	H	H	H	141	48
3m	OH	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	185	40
3n	OH	H	H	H	H	238d	45
3o	OH	H	H	H	H	241d	40
3p	OH	H	Cl	H	H	248d	38
3q	OH	H	H	H	H	224d	38

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis. **Compounds a-m: R=phenyl; n: 2-pyridyl, o: 2-furyl, p: 2-furyl, q: 2-thienyl.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. M. V. Kaulgud, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, for facilities.

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Synthesis of some New Arylazoisoxazoles

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Manuscript received 2 May 1988, revised 23 September 1988,
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BIOLOGICAL importance of azo compounds is well-known¹ and other useful chemotherapeutics², e.g. *N,N*-bis(2-chlorophenyl)-*p*-phenylazoaniline has been found to possess tumor inhibitory activity³. Furthermore, isoxazoles also have pharmacological⁴ interest and are found in nature⁵. It has been observed that the activity of azo linkage increases on the incorporation of suitable heterocyclic nuclei⁶. These studies prompted us to synthesise some new

compounds (1) as possible antineoplastic agents in which the isoxazole moiety is linked at one side of azo linkage in order to enhance the overall activity of the azo group.

1

where R and R' represent various substituents.

The compounds reported herein have been synthesised by reacting various substituted anilines with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis, and ir, nmr and mass spectral studies.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Parkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, uv-vis spectra on a Carl-Zeiss Specord spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (using TMS as internal standard) on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 instrument and mass spectra (70 eV) on a Jeol IMS-D × 300 spectrophotometer. All melting points are uncorrected.

1-Aminophenyl-3-arylhydrazonobutane-1,3-dione: Appropriate derivative of aniline (0.01 ml) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (4 ml), and water (5 ml), and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. To it, cooled aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g) was added. The resulting diazonium salt was filtered in already cooled solution mixture of sodium acetate (6.94 g) and alcohol (25 ml) containing 2,4-pentanedione (0.01 mol). The product

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF SOME SUBSTITUTED-ARYLAZOISOXAZOLES (1)*

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Mol. formula
1.	H	H	88	70	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O
2.	2-OH	H	140	60	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂
3.	3-Cl	H	185	64	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl
4.	4-Cl	H	190	62	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl
5.	2-OH ₂	H	164	66	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O
6.	4-OH ₂	H	160	68	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O
7.	4-OH ₂ -3-NO ₂	H	161	63	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂
8.	4-Cl-2-NO ₂	H	191	60	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
9.	3-NO ₂	H	238	67	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂
10.	4-NO ₂	H	200	67	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂
11.	2-OCH ₃	H	107	62	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂
12.	4-Br	H	244	68	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OClBr
13.	H	2-Cl	181	71	Brown	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl
14.	2-NO ₂	2-Cl	210	66	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
15.	3-NO ₂	2-Cl	201	64	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
16.	2-CH ₃	2-Cl	164	62	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OCl
17.	4-CH ₃	2-Cl	135	63	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OCl
18.	2-OCH ₃	2-Cl	168	60	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
19.	4-CH ₃ -3-NO ₂	2-Cl	210	61	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
20.	4-Br	2-Cl	285	66	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OBrCl
21.	3-Cl	2-Cl	187	63	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl ₂

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and C analyses.